

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Solving P° Multi-Criteria Optimization Problem of Agricultural Production Using the Weighted Sum Method

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Introduction. Today, the efficient use of resources and ensuring long-term system stability are among the most critical issues in agriculture. Specifically, the growing demand for food, coupled with limited water, land, and energy resources, requires approaches that simultaneously consider economic efficiency, environmental sustainability, and social factors. Therefore, agricultural planning often needs to optimize several goals at once: increasing economic profit, reducing production costs, limiting water consumption, and using other resources wisely [1–3].

In this research, the multi-objective optimization model for agricultural production proposed in [4] was reviewed and improved as follows.

Multi-Objective Optimization Model.

Objective functions:

$$f_1(x, z) = \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{j \in J} q_{ij} x_{ij} + \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{k \in K} \hat{q}_{ik} z_{ik} \rightarrow \min, \quad (1)$$

$$f_2(x, z) = \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{j \in J} P_{ij} a_{ij} x_{ij} + \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{k \in K} \hat{P}_{ik} z_{ik} \rightarrow \max, \quad (2)$$

$$f_3(x, z) = \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{j \in J} \omega_{ij} x_{ij} + \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{k \in K} \hat{\omega}_{ik} z_{ik} \rightarrow \min. \quad (3)$$

Constraints:

$$\sum_{i \in I} a_{ij} x_{ij} - \sum_{i \in I} y_{ij} \geq A_j, \quad \forall j \in J, \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I} z_{ik} \geq B_k, \quad \forall k \in K, \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} b_{jm} y_{ij} \geq \sum_{k \in K} \hat{b}_{ikm} z_{ik}, \quad \forall i \in I, \forall m \in M, \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} t_{ij} x_{ij} + \sum_{k \in K} \hat{t}_{ik} z_{ik} \leq T_i, \quad \forall i \in I, \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} x_{ij} \leq S_i, \quad \forall i \in I, \quad (8)$$

$$0 \leq y_{ij} \leq a_{ij}x_{ij}, \quad \forall i \in I, \forall j \in J, \quad (9)$$

$$0 \leq x_{ij} \leq \delta_{ij}X_{ij}^{\max}, \quad \forall i \in I, \forall j \in J, \quad (10)$$

$$0 \leq z_{ik} \leq \gamma_{ik}Z_{ik}^{\max}, \quad \forall i \in I, \forall k \in K. \quad (11)$$

We define the set of feasible solutions satisfying constraints (4)–(11) as D . The detailed problem statement, including the definitions of indices, parameters, and decision variables, is fully described in [4].

Solution Algorithm. Solving the three-objective problem (1)–(3) directly and simultaneously complicates the practical computing process. Therefore, it is appropriate to normalize the objectives and then transform them into a single-objective linear programming problem using the weighted sum method [5].

The algorithm consists of the following steps:

Step 1. Finding extreme values for each objective. To ensure correct normalization, the minimum and maximum possible values for each objective within the feasible region D are determined beforehand by solving individual optimization problems:

$$F_r^{\min} = \min_{(x,z) \in D} f_r(x, z), \quad F_r^{\max} = \max_{(x,z) \in D} f_r(x, z), \quad r \in \{1, 2, 3\}.$$

Step 2. Normalization. Since the objectives have different units of measurement, we scale them to the interval $[0, 1]$. In this step, all objectives are converted into a minimization form:

$$\begin{aligned} F_1^{\text{norm}}(x, z) &= \frac{f_1(x, z) - F_1^{\min}}{F_1^{\max} - F_1^{\min}}, \\ F_2^{\text{norm}}(x, z) &= \frac{F_2^{\max} - f_2(x, z)}{F_2^{\max} - F_2^{\min}}, \\ F_3^{\text{norm}}(x, z) &= \frac{f_3(x, z) - F_3^{\min}}{F_3^{\max} - F_3^{\min}}, \end{aligned}$$

where $F_r^{\max} \neq F_r^{\min}$, $r \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

As a result, the values of F_1^{norm} , F_2^{norm} , F_3^{norm} range between 0 and 1, making it possible to compare and combine them directly.

Step 3. Constructing a single objective function using the weighted sum method. In this step, weights representing the priorities of the decision-maker are selected:

$$0 \leq \alpha_1 \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq \alpha_2 \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq \alpha_3 \leq 1, \quad \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 = 1.$$

The single objective function is then formulated as:

$$F(x, z) = \alpha_1 F_1^{\text{norm}}(x, z) + \alpha_2 F_2^{\text{norm}}(x, z) + \alpha_3 F_3^{\text{norm}}(x, z) \rightarrow \min. \quad (12)$$

By substituting the original objective functions (1)–(3) into (12) and simplifying, we obtain the following compact objective function:

$$\begin{aligned}
F(x, z) = & \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{j \in J^i} (\alpha_1 k_1 q_{ij} - \alpha_2 k_2 P_{ij} a_{ij} + \alpha_3 k_3 \omega_{ij}) x_{ij} \\
& + \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{k \in K^i} \left(\alpha_1 k_1 \widehat{q}_{ik} - \alpha_2 k_2 \widehat{P}_{ik} + \alpha_3 k_3 \widehat{\omega}_{ik} \right) z_{ik},
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{F_1^{\max} - F_1^{\min}}, \quad k_2 = \frac{1}{F_2^{\max} - F_2^{\min}}, \quad k_3 = \frac{1}{F_3^{\max} - F_3^{\min}}.$$

As a result, we obtain a single-objective linear programming problem consisting of objective function (13) subject to constraints (4)–(11).

Step 4. Pareto Analysis. Various combinations of the weights $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ are selected. For each combination, the optimization problem (13) is solved subject to constraints (4)–(11), and the corresponding values of f_1, f_2, f_3 are collected. Then, dominated solutions are removed, and the remaining ones are considered as Pareto-efficient solutions.

Conclusion. In this study, a three-objective linear optimization model was presented for the joint planning of crop production and livestock farming, incorporating cost, profit, and water consumption criteria. The model includes constraints related to product and livestock demand, feed balance, as well as resource and land limitations. The multi-criteria problem was transformed into a single-objective linear programming problem using normalization and the weighted sum method. The proposed approach is particularly suitable for practical planning in regions with limited water resources.

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